

Properties of RF magnetron sputtered SnO₂:CuO (50:50) thin films

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Abstract

Tin oxide (SnO₂) and copper oxide (CuO) are widely used TCOs. SnO₂ is a *n*-type semiconductor with wide energy gap of 3.7 eV. CuO is a *p*-type semiconductor with energy gap of 1.5 eV. Because of their unique electrical and optical properties, both SnO₂ and CuO have wide range of applications such as gas sensor(1), flat panel display(2), photo catalyst (3) etc. Thin films of SnO₂:CuO (50:50) were deposited on pre-cleaned quartz substrate using RF sputtering with different sputtering powers. The XRD analysis shows that the prepared films were amorphous in nature. The uniform morphological feature was realized from the HRSEM micrographs. The optical property studied by UV-Vis NIR spectrophotometer shows that the transmittance of the film decreases with increase in the sputtering power and the band gap decreases from 3.80 eV to 3.59 eV with increase in the sputtering power.

Keywords: Mixed oxide, thin films, physical properties

References

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